

Prediction of Moment Distribution for One-Way Slab Systems Based on Structural Drawing Recognition

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Abstract

The structural design of one-way slabs typically relies on moment coefficients provided by the American Concrete Institute (ACI) code, which are determined based on factors such as span length and the number of spans. However, when design conditions deviate from ACI criteria, engineers must manually recalculate these coefficients based on structural drawings a time consuming task, especially in the early design stages with frequent revisions. This study proposes a machine learning approach that predicts moment coefficients beyond the constraints of ACI code conditions by incorporating variations in span lengths and column heights. A dataset was generated based on ACI 318-19 provisions, considering different span ratios and support conditions. Using the YOLO model, input variables such as the ratio of adjacent spans and the ratio of the longest span to column height were extracted directly from structural drawings. These were used to predict negative moments at slab ends and positive moments at mid-span through a linear regression model. The proposed model achieved an error rate of less than 5% in predicting moment values for interior spans, demonstrating its potential as a rapid and efficient alternative for structural decision-making during the preliminary and schematic design phases. Furthermore, the proposed approach provides a basis for extending moment prediction to more complex systems, such as shell and spatial structures, by enabling early-stage estimation of stress concentration through visual interpretation.

Keywords: Image Detection Model, One-Way Slab Design, Linear Regression Model, Design Automation, Schematic Design, Preliminary Design

1. Introduction

The construction industry has long strived for more efficient designs, particularly during the schematic design phase, where frequent design changes present significant challenges. During this phase, designers often prioritize creativity while neglecting or insufficiently considering structural requirements, leading to a diminished emphasis on structural analysis, as noted by Abdullah et al. [1]. In practice, even when a design is completed, the entire process may need to be restarted if subsequent structural analysis reveals instability in the structure. Additionally, engineers have been working for years to document information from construction drawings using artificial neural networks by Lv, Xiaolei, et al.[2]. Notable advancements include methods for accurately extracting text from drawings without errors, distinguishing identical 2D drawings with design inconsistencies or differing presentation styles, as demonstrated by Schönfelder et al. [3], and developing models to automatically detect common design errors in CAD 2D drawings, as reported by Huang et al. [4].

You Only Look Once (YOLO), a convolutional neural network, is a highly effective model for detecting structural objects in drawings, as explored by Zhao et al. [5]. Research efforts have focused on identifying building components in 2D as-built drawings, such as the location of structural elements,

grids, or text, as discussed by Zhao et al. [6]. However, a significant limitation of detection models is their inability to establish relationships or interactions between detected objects, making these models unsuitable for direct application in structural analysis, as highlighted by Chen et al. [7].

The objective of this study is to apply object detection techniques to early-stage design scenarios using floor plans. While conventional methods such as Building Information Modeling (BIM) or commercial analysis programs calculate moment values based on models generated from drawings or simulation-based modeling, the proposed approach enables faster and more intuitive moment estimation without the need for explicit modeling or potential conflicts between designers and engineers. Furthermore, this study proposes a novel method that integrates linear regression or predictive models into structural design. With continued development, this approach is expected to be applicable to more complex structural systems, such as solid and spatial structures, enabling effective prediction of stress-concentrated areas.

The proposed methodology enables a rapid response to situations, where the moment values acting on one-way slabs during the schematic design phase fail to meet the standards of the American Concrete Institute (ACI). To address this challenge, the proposed approach effectively supports the completion of design processes and ensures compliance with structural requirements, particularly during the schematic design phase, in real-world construction settings.

Figure 1: (a) Detection and Recognition of structural Drawing,
 (b) Prediction and analysis of bending moment for the equivalent frame of A-A cross-section

2. Detection and recognition of structural members in structural drawing

Figure 2: Original image (Left), YOLOv9 Detected image (Right)

The framework of the model is based on YOLOv9 architecture, which incorporates an advanced structure for object detection, characterized by efficient feature extraction, robust processing blocks, and improved gradient information flow. The architecture employs convolutional blocks that integrate a 2D convolutional layer, batch normalization, and the SiLU activation function into a single operation, optimizing computational efficiency. Additionally, YOLOv9 includes an auto-padding mechanism that dynamically computes padding values when not explicitly defined. For example, a kernel size of 3 with a stride of 1 result in a padding value of 1, while a kernel size of 1 with a stride of 1 result in no padding. These foundational blocks ensure adaptability and consistency in feature extraction by Wang et al [8]

2.1 Object detection in YOLOv9 performance

The object detection capabilities of YOLOv9 can also be applied to structural drawings, by utilizing data labeling, a model was trained to classify four categories present in structural diagrams: *Column*, *Beam*, *Girder*, and *Wall*. The trained model was able to detect these four classes with an accuracy of 94%. Compared to Columns, which have clearly defined shapes, the model also successfully recognized Girders and Beams, which share similar characteristics. Additionally, the model demonstrated strong learning performance in Class, Object, and Segment detection tasks.

2.2.1 Loss functions in YOLOv9

- Segmentation loss is used if the YOLOv9 framework supports segmentation tasks in addition to object detection. The purpose of this loss is to quantify the difference between the predicted segmentation result and the actual segmentation result (ground truth).
- Box loss measures the error between the predicted bounding box and the ground truth box. The purpose of this loss is minimizing the difference in location, size, and shape of the predicted and ground truth boxes.
- Objectness loss determines whether an object is present in each grid cell. The purpose of this loss is to improve the model's confidence in predicting whether a region contains an object or not.
- Classification loss ensures the model accurately predicts the class label for an object in the bounding box. The purpose of this loss is to reduce the error between the predicted class probabilities and the ground truth class.

Figure 3: Training losses with respect to epoch using YOLOv9

2.2 Object recognition using YOLOv9 output

In ACI 6.5.1 standard, the design moment coefficients for the maximum moments of one-way slabs are specified separately for each end. To apply this provision, five conditions must be satisfied, one of which, as indicated in the drawings, is that the difference in span lengths between adjacent spans must not exceed 20%. This condition serves as a guideline for determining the range when generating moment values for one-way slabs as training data in regression models, ensuring that the span length differences do not exceed 20%.

Utilizing YOLO v9, the coordinates of information related to beams, girders, and columns present in the drawing are extracted, and the extracted information is used to separately classify the data into layers. The reason for classifying the layers separately is that inputting data with dimensions greater than three into a two-dimensional Data frame is complex and has a high risk of errors. When viewing the Data frame as one large coordinate plane, it is possible to input the corresponding structural information at the specific coordinates. While the coordinate data can provide information about the length and orientation of the members, there is an issue with the accuracy of the predicted length values. The coordinates provided by the predictions do not always represent precise lengths, making them unsuitable for accurate measurements. This issue can be resolved using the dimension annotations provided in the structural drawings.

2.2.1 Dimensioning technique detected objects and text with YOLOv9

In design cases when the coordinates or positions of structural members on an image have been identified using object detection, finding the dimensions of the members can be achieved by combining the features of text detection and object detection. Since text can be detected using YOLOv9, the coordinates of the dimensions can also be identified. In typical structural drawings, dimensions are represented with vertical text for vertical members and horizontal text for horizontal members. Therefore, information about the length of a member can be detected through the orientation and coordinates of the text using the YOLOv9 model. By leveraging multiple layers, the information of a member present at a specific coordinate can be stored in the same location. For the saved data frame, the second layer can store information indicating whether the member is "Horizontal" if the length is longer horizontally, or "Vertical" if it is longer vertically, based on the member's coordinates.

Figure 4: Object recognition process using coordinates detected through YOLO
 (a) Coordinate Matching process, (b) Output on the drawing after coordinate matching

If the direction of the number entered for a dimension is horizontal, the objects with the horizontal property corresponding to the y-coordinate of the number's center point can be connected along the y-axis. This allows the dimensions of the structural members to be input into the third layer of the data frame.

2.3 Design Method and Characteristics of One-Way Slabs According to the ACI Code

After storing the positions and characteristics of members using the multi-layer approach, the relationships between members can be identified based on the coordinate values of the image data in the data frame. This study examines the moment values at both ends and the center of the most common elements, such as spandrel beams, girders, and general beams, while excluding special beams like transfer beams. When calculating the moments of frame structures, the ACI 6.5.2 one-way slab standard provides specific moment coefficients for this purpose.

Therefore, the calculation of the moment values at both ends and the center of members in slabs with three or more bays using an analysis model or precise analysis program, it is possible to reverse-engineer the moment coefficients used in the ACI 6.5.2 code. The converted moment coefficient values can then be used to train a linear regression model.

2.4 Data Generation and Preprocessing

Figure 5: 2D Equivalent Frame Model for Input Dataset generation

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{L_1}{L_2} \quad \alpha_2 = \frac{L_2}{L_3} \quad \alpha_3 = \frac{H}{2L_1} \quad (1)$$

$$0.3 \leq \alpha_3 \leq 0.5 \quad (2)$$

Figure 6: Generated Moment distribution dataset histogram

The training set for the learning data was implemented using analysis code to draw the Bending Moment Diagram (BMD) of the frame structure consisting of columns and beams. By adjusting the ratio of adjacent span lengths, moment values were generated, and these moment values were divided by the input distributed load and span length to calculate moment coefficients. The input variables for training the prediction model were the span ratios between adjacent bays and the ratio of span length to column height Equation (1), which were derived from the geometric properties of the frame. The output variables were the moment coefficients, calculated by dividing the moment values at the ends and mid-spans of the beams by the applied load and corresponding span length, making them independent of specific load magnitudes.

The values generated were cross validated by comparing them with results from a commercial analysis program, achieving an average accuracy of 96.7% between the analysis model and the commercial analysis program. The moment distributions generated include the moment values at both ends and the center of horizontal members (e.g., spans AB, BC, and CD in Figure 7). As a result, three coefficients were generated for each member between columns. In the context of frame structure design, α_1 and α_2 represent the ratios of adjacent spans. According to ACI Code 6.5.1, the lengths of adjacent spans must not differ by more than 20%. Therefore, the range for α_1 and α_2 is constrained between 0.8 and 1.2 to comply with ACI requirements. On the other hand, α_3 represents the ratio of span length to column height and follows the range specified in Equation (2), between 0.3 and 0.5. Based on these constraints, 50,000 moment coefficient data points were generated using the analysis model. The generated data was utilized to train a multiple linear regression model.

3. Validation of the proposed model

3.1 Comparison of analysis and prediction model

Figure 7: 2D Equivalent Frame Predictive Model Part of Bending Moments Q-Q plots
 (a) Training Bending Moment Data, (b) Test Bending Moment Data

Figure 8: 2D Equivalent Frame Model analysis and Prediction

3.2 Moment value calculation for One-Way Slabs using the ACI code

In figure 8 is described the comparison of bending moment diagram. The moment calculation method using the ACI code shows little difference in positive moments, but it was observed that negative moments differ by an average of over 50%. This is because the ACI code adopts a conservative design approach for the central portion of one-way slabs where moments are applied.

Figure 9: Comparison of a bending moment diagram analysis and ACI code

4. Comparison of 3D full frame model and predictive model

4.1 Full frame 3D model and 2D equivalent frame model

Figure 10: 3D Full Frame Model convert to 2D Full Frame Model

The left image in Figure 10 represents the 3D frame structure, while the right image shows its conversion into a 2D frame, clearly displaying the moment values for each member. The frame model is based on the conditions of a 5-story, 3-span, and 4-span frame structure with span lengths of 9, 9, and 7.2 meters. Among these, the frame structure model for the 3-span will be compared with the Predict model trained using the analysis model.

Although the values generated by the analysis model may differ as they are based on the Equivalent Frame Model (EFM), this approach is preferred over calculating precise moment values for a complex 3D model. By Instead, it calculates simplified moment values based on the representative floor, allowing for efficient utilization even in the structural drawings of the initial design phase, as demonstrated by Lagomarsino et al. [9].

4.2 2D Full frame and 2D equivalent frame

Figure 11: Comparison of Moment Distribution for 2D Full Frame and 2D Equivalent Frame predictive Models

When comparing the multi-story 2D model analyzed using a precise analysis program with the four-span equivalent frame using the prediction model, the negative moment values of the slab, excluding the slab end moments, showed a maximum difference of 2.1%, while the positive moment values exhibited a maximum difference of 3.5%. In the precise frame analysis, the slab end moment values from the 2nd to the 4th floor showed a relatively larger difference compared to the prediction model. However, this

discrepancy arises due to the multi-story structure. When comparing the interior span moment values with each interior slab moment value in Figure 11, an error rate of less than 5% was observed.

5. Conclusion

The Schematic Design phase typically focuses on design without verifying structural safety, as noted by Abdullah et al. [5] However, this approach often leads to significant time consumption due to later modifications when the design fails to comply with structural codes such as the ACI Code. To address this issue, this study proposes a rapid moment calculation method for the Schematic Design phase using YOLOv9 and a linear regression model. By applying the YOLOv9 model, structural components in drawings (e.g., beams, columns) were detected. The detected results were processed through a recognition step using Pandas dataframe, allowing the spatial relationships among the detected objects to be stored effectively. For training the linear regression model, an analysis model was used to generate a dataset, varying the span lengths between slabs and column heights according to ACI standards. The trained model achieved an R^2 value of at least 0.9, demonstrating high accuracy. Furthermore, when comparing the Analysis Model, ACI Code, and Prediction Model using the Equivalent Frame Model, the ACI Code showed a 50% more conservative estimation in terms of fixed-end moments, whereas the Prediction Model exhibited nearly equivalent performance to the Analysis Model. When comparing the Prediction Model with a High-Fidelity Analysis Model, it was confirmed that the 2D frame representation of the 3D precision analysis model closely matched the baseline floor values.

In summary, the proposed method enables a visual representation of rapid moment calculations during the Schematic Design phase. This allows designers to quickly estimate and select design alternatives more efficiently than conventional methods. The long-term vision of this study is to extend the application of this approach to reinforcement detailing and nonlinear slab design in the early design phase. Moreover, the proposed method lays the foundation for future applications in more complex structural systems such as shell and spatial structures, where early-stage visual estimation of stress concentrations can support efficient design exploration.

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